

SATISFACTORY

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CERTH ¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
D	Deliverable
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
IMS	Intelligent Manufacturing Systems
M	Month
NoI	Network of Interest
PFS	Presentation and Feedback Session
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020).

This document presents the SatisFactory Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP), defining the strategy and implementation measures envisioned to efficiently communicate about project objectives and disseminate project outputs in order to ensure the best exploitation of its results.

The SatisFactory DCP will be systematically updated at M12, M24 and M36. A version of the DCP will be then inserted into each project periodic report.

The DCP is structured in order to answer the following questions – WHY, WHO, TO WHOM, WHAT, WHAT FOR, HOW, WHEN? – and to present relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

1. PURPOSE – WHY?

The SatisFactory project aims to enhance and enrich the manufacturing working environment towards attractive factories of the future that encompass key enabling technologies such as augmented reality, wearable and ubiquitous computing as well as and customised social communication platforms coupled with experience design and gamification techniques for the efficient transfer of knowledge and experience among employees.

1.1 DEFINITIONS OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION²

According to the European Commission, communication on projects “is a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”. The dissemination of the project outputs is “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The SatisFactory communication and dissemination objectives are:

- To promote EU research and innovation in manufacturing and ICT domains, and beyond;
- To raise awareness about innovative approaches for enhancing workplace attractiveness and key technologies for improving industrial development in Europe;
- To influence the attitudes of decision-makers towards a stronger support to European smart factories;
- To support SatisFactory activities and findings, making the results developed through the project available to the widest audience and enhancing the exploitation potential.

² The definitions of the key terms “communication” and “dissemination” used in this section originate from the European Commission participant portal website.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

2. DISSEMINATION PLAYERS – WHO?

WP6 is led by SIGMA, a company with an extensive expertise in communication and dissemination activities related to research and innovation projects. Most partners are engaged to support SatisFactory’s communication, dissemination and networking activities, for example by:

1. disseminating links to SatisFactory’s activities through their own websites and social media;
2. providing the task leader SIGMA with news on the project’s progress, which will be used to feed SatisFactory online and off-line communication;
3. promoting SatisFactory during internal and external events.

Table 1 – WP6 efforts in person-month

WP6 EFFORTS IN PERSON-MONTH					
	T6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plans	T6.2 Project visibility & branding	T6.3 Project events and International Collaboration	T.4 VR-enabled end-users training to SatisFactory solution	Total per partner
CERTH	2	0	3	8	13
SIGMA	4	11	12	3	30
Fraunhofer	0	0	0	0	0
COMAU	1	0	0	2	3
EPFL	4	4	2	0	10
ISMB	2	0	2	0	4
ABE	1	2	2	2	7
Regola	0	0	0	0	0
SUNLIGHT	1	1	2	2	6
GlassUP	1	1	2	0	4
Expected PM contribution per task	16	19	25	17	77

= Task leader

3. TARGET AUDIENCES – TO WHOM?

The six main identified target groups are listed in the following table:

Table 2 – Target groups

	CATEGORIES	EXAMPLES OF MAIN STAKEHOLDERS
	Industry decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-level representatives of manufacturing companies in various sectors (e.g. automotive, energy, etc.) - Professional organizations such as Intelligent Manufacturing Systems (IMS), and the European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)
	Research communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart manufacturing researchers - Specific ICT research communities (e.g. IoT, Augmented Reality)
	Policy-makers and facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Institutions (European Commission, European Science Foundation, MEPs) - National public authorities (industrial committees, ministry and regional councils) - Standardization Bodies (such as CEN, DIN)
	Pilot sites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operators in pilot plants (workers, technicians, managers, etc.)
	Related initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Related EU-funded projects - ETPs (MANUFUTURE technology platform) and clusters
	EU citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals and civil society

4. MESSAGES – WHAT?

Key information and solutions for building the industrial future of Europe will be disseminated during the project lifetime.

Table 3 – Key information to be disseminated

Key information and solutions to be disseminated by the project	
Information on:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and innovation activities (implemented by the project, or relevant to the project area implemented by external stakeholders); • Project results;
Solutions (innovative approaches and technologies) for:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing factories productivity and efficiency; • Enhancing the attractiveness of working environment in factories.

Finally, the upgrading of manufacturing industry is expected to support the industrial economy and employment in Europe.

5. EXPECTED OUTCOMES – WHAT FOR?

The communication and dissemination plan is carefully designed to address the identified target groups in the most effective way. The expected outcomes of SatisFactory's communication include:

- a large number of stakeholders being more aware of ideas and technologies for building the industrial future of Europe;
- scientists, researchers and manufacturers convinced that they should pay a special attention to enhancing the quality and attractiveness of working environment in factories, and in making them attractive to young talents;
- if possible, economic and policy decision-makers encouraged in supporting the industrial economy and employment in Europe by promoting novel ICT technologies for industry;
- lastly, and above all, a broad dissemination of new, disruptive ideas, concepts and solutions for the enhancement of work life and manufacturing productivity.

SatisFactory key target audience and the expected impact of communication and dissemination activities are listed in the following table.

Table 4 – Expected impact on key target audiences

SATISFACTORY KEY TARGET AUDIENCES						
Expected impact:	Industry decision-makers	Research communities	Policy-makers and facilitators	Pilot sites	Related initiatives	EU citizens
• Will be more aware of ideas and technologies for building the industrial future of Europe	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
• Will help foster EU research and innovation on SatisFactory related technologies	✓	✓	✓		✓	
• Will be convinced to pay a special attention to enhancing the quality and attractiveness of working environment in factories	✓	✓		✓		
• Will support industrial economy and employment in Europe by promoting novel ICT technologies for industry	✓		✓			
• Will be directly affected by the outcomes of the research, and will provide feedback on project activities and results				✓		
• May adopt SatisFactory's technologies and solutions for improving factories efficiency and attractiveness	✓	✓				

6. TOOLS AND ACTIVITIES – HOW?

This section explains SatisFactory strategy to deliver key information in the most effective way. In order to meet the objectives previously defined, various tools and products related to communication and dissemination activities will be developed during the project lifetime. These tools and activities will provide accessible information to stakeholders and facilitate awareness raising.

6.1 PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

6.1.1 Project logo

The logo was selected by partners on the occasion of the project kick-off meeting on January 22, 2015.

Figure 1 – SatisFactory logo

The project logo was designed to picture the ideas of:

- Attractive place for workers (sunshine colours);
- Re-adaptation of production facilities with human-centred technologies (conventional symbol of factory surrounded by dynamic symbol of human);
- Innovation (yellow colour) and ICT technology (digital-like squares coming out of the factory chimney);
- Knowledge-sharing (circle).

6.1.2 Graphic charter

The graphical identity derived from the project logo has been developed at M1. It details the use of logotype, colours and fonts to be used by the project. All project materials are developed in line with this graphic charter.

Main colours

	ORANGE	OCHRE	YELLOW	GREY	BLACK
RGB	246 142 30	255 209 117	255 206 0	88 88 90	0 0 0
HEX	F68E1E	FFD175	FFCE00	58585A	000000

Secondary colours

	ORANGE	DARK BLUE	ORANGE2	BROWN	LIGHT BLUE
RGB	246 142 30	0 124 169	255 159 57	169 93 10	30 188 246
HEX	F68E1E	007CA9	FF9F39	A95D0A	1EBCF6

Figure 2 – SatisFactory colours from graphic charter

6.1.3 Project templates

Following the definition of the project visual identity, project templates were developed at M3 to ensure that all documents produced by the project are sharing the same design and remain consistent with the project image during the entire project period. SatisFactory's set of templates includes templates for project Deliverables, PowerPoint presentations and Newsletters.

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Table 5 – Project templates

PROJECT TEMPLATES		
SatisFactory's set of templates:	Already done?	Due date
Project deliverables	✓	M3
Project PowerPoint presentations	✓	M3
Newsletters	✓	M6

Figure 3 – SatisFactory's templates (deliverables and PowerPoint presentation)

6.2 NETWORK OF INTEREST

- **Contact email**

The contact email info@satisfactory-project.eu was created at M2 and is added to all project communication materials and online tools. This contact email is managed by the dissemination and communication leader (SIGMA).

- **Newsletter audience**

SatisFactory is targeting various stakeholders (mainly from manufacturing and research sectors) through a communication mailing list called “network of interest” (NoI). The NoI list will be used when publishing the newsletter and communicating about events. All project partners have access to a shared file to suggest potential members from external organizations. Information on project activities, progress, outcomes and events, will be regularly flowed through newsletters sent from info@satisfactory-project.eu.

Currently (M6), the Network of interest is composed of 82 people, divided into 3 segments:

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- Project partners: 46 members
- Members suggested by partners: 30 members
- Subscribers to the newsletter: 6 members

The expected performance is 300 NoI contacts by the end of the project.

6.3 PROJECT PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

6.3.1 Reference project presentation

At M3 the project coordinator (CERTH) produced a preliminary PowerPoint presentation to highlight the project's key facts, concept and objectives. Partners can use this reference presentation to introduce the project and its activities when attending events.

6.3.2 Project flyer, brochure and poster

A promotional flyer and a poster have been designed at M3. The flyer describes the project's key facts, objectives and expected results so that the general public can quickly understand what the project is about. Two hundred copies of the flyer and ten copies of the poster have been printed and shared among partners in order to be handed out at events. A brochure containing the project results will be produced at M12 and updated at M30 to present the final outcomes of the project.

Table 6 – Project promotional materials

PROJECT PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS				
	Format	Copies	Due date	Done?
Flyer	15x21	x200	M3	✓
Poster	60x80	x10	M3	✓
Brochure	X	X	M12, M30	X

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IMPROVING

Workers satisfaction and safety

Industrial efficiency and productivity

CUTTING-EDGE TECHNOLOGIES & INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

Training and knowledge sharing tools

Systems for real-time decision support

Augmented reality for industry

Gamification approaches

ID CARD

Acronym: Satisfactory

Full Title: A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments

Start Date: 01/01/2015

Duration: 36 months

Programme: Horizon 2020

Partnership: Factories of the Future

Topic: "Developing smart factories that are attractive to workers"

www.satisfactory-project.eu

Satisfactory is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement n°1010102.

Figure 4 – Project flyer

6.3.3 Video trailer

A short video trailer is being produced (at M6) to promote the projects objectives and activities, and will be soon released online. The video aims to inform a wide audience about innovative solutions developed by project partners in order to create smart and attractive factories. To this end, the video will contain (1) interviews of project partners, (2) a presentation of the technologies developed all along the project and (3) shots from the three pilot plants. Interviews of project partners have been filmed during the 2nd Plenary Meeting, May 28-29, 2015, in Brussels. Easily shared on the web, and displayed on wide screens at events, the video trailer will be a very effective way to communicate.

Figure 5 – SatisFactory video trailer

6.4 PROJECT WEBSITE AND SEO

A project website (<http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/>) was created at M3 and is a deliverable (D6.1) at M6. The SatisFactory website is constantly updated with the latest project news and will be continuously improved all along the project lifetime.

6.4.1 Website strategy

The website constitutes a key communication tool to increase project visibility and impact towards communities of industry decision-makers, researchers and the general public. Initially due at M6, online at M3 and constantly updated, the SatisFactory website (D6.1) contains all relevant information about the project and related topics (SatisFactory objectives, information, news, event announcements, public reports, analysis, links to related initiatives). The main objective of the website is to spread the project goals and results as widely as possible. SatisFactory's website is released under the Creative Commons (CC) license, a public copyright license. The website development and maintenance is lead by SIGMA.

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Table 7 – SatisFactory website: key facts

SatisFactory website – Key facts	
Website URL:	http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/
Main objective	The project website will spread the project objectives and results as widely as possible
License	Creative Commons license
Target audience	At least 8000 visitors will have accessed the website by the end of the project

Priority was given to news about the project progress, a presentation of SatisFactory solutions and technologies, and their implementation in the three pilot sites. The template used (Porcelain) is especially adapted to this use and allows highlighting the core messages in a visually appealing slider.

6.4.2 Website structure

The overall structure of the website is the following:

Figure 6 – Website structure

The website homepage was given special care in order to give direct access to a short introduction of the project, show the main SatisFactory concepts and link to the website key contents, as shown below:

Figure 7 – SatisFactory website homepage

The website is fully integrated with the project social media, as both tools are complementary for SatisFactory online presence strategy.

6.4.3 Website analytics

- **Expected quantitative results (Key Performance Indicators - KPIs)**

Close monitoring based on analytical tools – such as Google Analytics – and on-page and off-page Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) will be used to improve the overall website's efficiency.

The website is expected rank among the Top 10/Top 3 Search Engine Results Page (SERP) using the following 3 predefined key expressions: SatisFactory project; Horizon 2020 satisfaction industry; satisfaction augmented reality industry.

Table 8 – Website KPIs

	Expected quantitative results			
	At M6	At M12	At M24	M36
Number of unique visitors/month	100	200	250	300
Minimum average visit duration	3'	3'	3'	3'
Position in SERPs on 3 predefined key expressions	Top 10	Top 5	Top 5	Top 3

- **Early results of SatisFactory's website impact (from Google Analytics)**

Preliminary metrics of the website attendance are shown below. Further updates and analysis will be provided in each iteration of the D6.4 deliverable (Report on dissemination activities), the first one being planned for M12.

Table 9 – Website early results

Date	Sessions /month	Users /month	Page/visit	Average visit duration (mins)	% of visits from social networks
March 2015	64	45	2,5	02:43	0%
April 2015	538	341	2,8	03:15	21%
May 2015	870	741	1,6	02:13	14%

Figure 8 – Website visitors: new users

Sessions by Country

■ United States ■ France ■ Greece ■ (not set) ■ Belgium ■ Italy ■ Other

Figure 9 – Website visitors: sessions by country

A constant monitoring using appropriate tools (web analytics, survey...) and performance measurements will be done, in order to measure the quality and success of SatisFactory communication and dissemination efforts, and to readjust actions whenever required.

6.5 PROJECT SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

Social media activities contribute to increase the project impact and foster networking & clustering between targeted stakeholders. The project uses social media to share relevant news as widely as possible and engage with identified target groups in Europe and beyond.

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The project online community development will leverage on interactions with already existing communities, thus legitimating SatisFactory in the field.

Figure 10 – Social media accounts

6.5.1 Twitter

A project Twitter account (@SatisFactoryEU) was created at M2 and is fully operational since M4. The project community manager (SIGMA) uses social media dashboard applications (Tweetadder and Hootsuite) to curate information from influencers and to schedule posts. Twitter analytics tools ensure Social Media Optimisation (SMO).

Table 10 – Twitter analytics

TWITTER ANALYTICS		
	Current situation (M6)	Expected impact by the end of the project (M36)
Twitter followers	149	300
Average of tweets posted every week	15	> 5

Figure 11 – Early results of SatisFactory's Twitter analytics

6.5.2 LinkedIn

A project LinkedIn account (SatisFactory H2020 Project) was created at M2 on the basis of a “company page” template, enabling high visibility. LinkedIn is convenient for professional purposes, enabling project partners to add the project LinkedIn webpage to their online LinkedIn CV.

The expected impact is:

- 100 LinkedIn subscribers by the end of the project
- At least 1 LinkedIn post published every two weeks

6.5.3 Facebook

A project Facebook account (SatisFactory H2020 Project) was created at M2 to relays the website news.

Expected impact:

- 100 Facebook likes by the end of the project
- At least 1 post every week

6.5.4 YouTube

A project YouTube channel (SatisFactory Project) was created at M2 to upload short videos introducing the project, its partnership, activities, as well as past event trailers. Currently, two videos are online, presenting:

- The Incident Detection tool, developed by CERTH.

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- SatisFactory participation to the “Affidabilità e Tecnologie” (A&T) exhibition in Turin, Lingotto Fiere, April 22-23, 2015. This video was created by REGOLA.

Figure 12 – YouTube video: Incident Detection by CERTH

Expected impact:

- At least 600 video views by the end of the project
- At least 10 videos published during the project

6.6 PROJECT PRESS RELEASES AND PUBLICATIONS

6.6.1 Press releases

A press release was prepared by CERTH at M2 to announce the launch of the project and then sent out to targeted media. This dissemination was carried out in synergy with all partners, relaying the press release through their networks.

6.6.2 Newsletter and email blasts

A newsletter will be issued every six months to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the project news and developments. The newsletter will be drafted by SIGMA and will contain major announcements related to project activities (report available, event announced, etc.). It will be circulated on partner's networks. A professional emailing solution (Mailchimp) is used to ensure the best delivery performance.

6.6.3 Research papers and articles

Project partners commit to publish technical articles, papers and reports presenting project activities and results in highly reputed journals and magazines to spread knowledge among

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the identified manufacturing and research target groups and ensure sustainable exploitation of project outcomes.

6.6.4 Public deliverables

A major expression of external dissemination is the production of deliverables. Over the entire project duration, the SatisFactory project consortium will produce 33 official deliverables. 21 of them will be made publicly available in the project website resources area in order to spread the project excellence and disseminate knowledge as widely as possible.

6.6.5 Follow-up tables of Dissemination and Communication activities

Shared sheets were created by SIGMA at the beginning of the project to easily share information among partners on dissemination and communication activities.

Four lists are available:

1. Follow-up list of partners' attendance to external events promoting SatisFactory, and their contribution: exhibition booth, distribution of flyers, etc.
2. Dissemination channels (newspapers, websites, social medias).
3. Network of interest (NoI): identified stakeholders interested by the SatisFactory project. This list will be used for disseminating project newsletters and promoting project events.
4. Published news and press releases about SatisFactory.

6.7 EVENTS AND NETWORKING

6.7.1 Presentation and Feedback Sessions (PFS)

- **Concept of the PFSs**

Every year, the project will organize a Presentation and feedback Session (PFS) by taking part to a major forum or trade show in the field of smart manufacturing to maximise the impact on potential clients. These conferences organised by the consortium will facilitate dissemination of the project results to manufacturing and research groups and represent an opportunity to receive valuable feedback from those stakeholders.

- **First PFS: ICT2015, 20-22 October 2015, Lisbon**

For its first Presentation and Feedback Session, SatisFactory applied to the ICT2015 exhibition, organized by DG Connect, which will be held on 20-22 October in Lisbon (for more details see Annex 1: Application to ICT2015 - Booth and Networking Session). Three project partners (SIGMA, CERTH and GlassUp) are managing the organisation of SatisFactory participation to ICT2015, wishing to set up both an exhibition booth and a networking session.

6.7.2 Contributions to external events

SatisFactory contribution to related external events - dealing for example with manufacturing, ICT, augmented reality, and others research and innovation area - will favour intense exchange of information and know-how with relevant target groups. The expected performance is a contribution to 10 external events.

As a first step, SatisFactory participated to the “Affidabilità e Tecnologie” (A&T) exhibition in Turin, Lingotto Fiere, April 22-23, 2015. SatisFactory booth was supported by REGOLA and COMAU, who also created a promotional video of the event.

Figure 13 – SatisFactory participation at the A&T exhibition, Turin, April 2015

6.7.3 End-users training sessions

A series of (at least 3) Virtual Reality enabled workers training to SatisFactory solution will be held towards the end of the project in cooperation with key stakeholder groups. The (one day) training sessions will ensure the deployment and scaling up of the developed solutions in other factories than the project demonstration sites. These sessions will also enable new users to experiment the solutions and to provide their feedback and eventually will allow to fine-tune the solutions and to prepare their commercialisation.

6.7.4 International Collaboration - Synergies with related on-going initiatives

Synergies and cross promotion with related projects is sought to help spreading the word about the project latest activities, achievements and coming events. International networking activities include organizations from other Factories of the Future projects, through the European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA). The SatisFactory consortium is also planning to liaise with the Intelligent Manufacturing Systems (IMS) thanks to partners' (EPFL and Fraunhofer FIT) business and research networks.

7. OVERALL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MANAGEMENT – WHEN?

7.1 ANALYTICS: IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND KPI'S MONITORING

This section recaps the expected impact of our communication and dissemination strategy (goals and objectives detailed in Section §1). A constant monitoring using appropriate tools (Web analytics, survey, etc.) and performance measurements (KPIs) will be done, in order to measure the quality and success of our communication and dissemination efforts, and to readjust actions whenever required. The following table lists the performance indicators and expected quantitative results for each communication and dissemination tools and activities.

Table 11 – Expected quantitative results

	EXPECTED QUANTITATIVE RESULTS			
	At M6	At M12	At M24	At M36
DISSEMINATION MAILING LIST				
• Number of subscribers	25	50	100	150
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
• Number of distributed project brochures/flyer	50	100	200	300
• Number of posters	10	10	20	20
WEBSITE				
• Position in SERPs on 3 predefined key expressions	Top 10	Top 5	Top 5	Top 3
• Number of unique visitors/month	100	200	250	300
• Minimum average visit duration	3'	3'	3'	3'
SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS				
Twitter				
• Number of followers	50	100	200	300
• Number of tweets per week	> 5	> 5	> 5	> 5
Facebook				
• Number of likes	15	30	60	100
• Number of posts per week	1	1	1	1
LinkedIn				

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• LinkedIn subscribers	15	30	60	100
• Number of posts per month	2	2	2	2
YouTube				
• Number of views	50	200	400	600
• Number of videos	2	4	7	10
PRESS RELEASES AND PUBLICATIONS				
Press release				
• Number of diffusion platforms	3	5	8	10
Newsletter				
• Number of recipients	30	60	120	180
PRESENTATION AND FEEDBACK SESSIONS				
• Minimum number of participants	X	50	50	100

7.2 TIMESCALE

The following timescale details when each communication and dissemination activity will be carried out. In the coming weeks and months next steps will include, inter alia, finalizing the video trailer, sending newsletters, organizing the first Presentation and Feedback Session. In addition, any relevant feedback will be taken into account to improve the future plans.

Figure 14 – Timescale

CONCLUSIONS

This document defines the Dissemination and Communication Plan at M6 of the SatisFactory project and details the corresponding targets, messages and best-suited tools that will be coped with during the overall project period.

As an Innovation Action (IA), Satisfactory needs concrete market outlets for its products – a set of cutting-edge technologies to be integrated in factory production lines. The dissemination and communication strategy has (1) to allow all relevant stakeholders to be informed about the project activities and outputs, (2) to ensure the highest exploitation potential of SatisFactory products by maximizing information received by potential customers and (3) to support European research and innovation in manufacturing and ICT, thus contributing to enhance industry competitiveness in Europe.

This requires, among other things, creating a corporate identity, publishing promotional materials (such as flyers and press releases), using online communication (project website and social networks), building synergies with related on-going initiatives and participating in high-level events to present the project's progress. The project is making steady progress toward the achievement of these dissemination and communication activities.

The D6.3 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” will be reviewed on an annual basis (M12, M24 and M36) on the occasion of the release of the D6.4 “Report on Dissemination Activities, Public Participation and Awareness”. This review will take into account the envisioned KPIs to assess the efficiency and success of such activities. In case the project fails to achieve its targeted objectives, corrective measures will be implemented with the aim of ensuring the project effective dissemination of its results and ultimately the sustainability of project outputs.

ANNEX – APPLICATION TO ICT2015, 20-22 OCTOBER, LISBON

Application to ICT2015, 20-22 October, Lisbon Booth

Proposal by Satisfactory EU FUNDED PROJECT

Main title: SatisFactory - A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments

Description for the Exhibition Catalogue

A 4.0 industrial revolution is underway with the introduction of new digital technologies within smart factories. SatisFactory is a three-year research project launched in January 2015 and funded by the European Commission under its Horizon 2020 programme. The project aims to research and develop emerging knowledge-driven training technologies (e.g. augmented reality, customized social communication platforms, gamification techniques, etc.) and wearable devices for the enhancement of innovation, productivity and scheduling of work in factory production lines, while improving workers satisfaction. The SatisFactory consortium is led by the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (Greece) and composed of Fraunhofer FIT (Germany), the Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (Switzerland), the Instituto Superiore Mario Boella (Italy), Sigma Orionis (France), Atlantis Engineering (Greece), Regola (Italy), GlassUp (Italy), Comau (Italy) and Systems Sunlight (Greece).

Web site: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/>

Description of what you wish to show

Two innovative tools: 1) An incident detection tool will show how images from smart depth sensors are analysed, to detect and track workers/visitors, to capture potential events and incidents, and to visualize them on an architectural map. 2) Augmented Reality glasses are proposed as an instructional support tool to on-the-plant manufacturing activities, with overlaid virtual symbology providing real-time instructions for the operators.

Describe the interaction with the exhibition visitors

1) A set of cameras will be installed to a selected area to demonstrate in real-time how the system could detect and track the visitors. The analysis of potential incidents will also be visualized on the system dashboard. 2) The AR glasses prototype will enable real temperature readings from thermocouples within a running system simulation, or/and mechanical parts guided-assembling. Glasses-guided solving of Rubik's cube will also be enabled as a more playful, engaging, example.

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What is innovative/visionary about the technology or activity you will demonstrate?

1) Event and incident detection is a very complex task, since it requests robust human detection and tracking, and a thorough analysis of humans' movements. SatisFactory effectively combines highly innovative techniques from various disciplines towards this direction. 2) Augmented-Reality Glasses designed for industry will enable hands-free instruction, guidance and training in manufacturing environments.

What is the expected impact for Europe in terms of re-industrialisation, jobs and societal aspects?

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies and innovative approaches. The project plans to increase the productivity and innovation potential of modern factories, while enhancing the skills of their workers as well as the safety and attractiveness of the industrial workplaces. After a test phase in pilot plants in Italy and Greece, the project is expected to widely disseminate its solutions in European factories.

Application to ICT2015, 20-22 October, Lisbon Networking session

Proposal by Satisfactory EU FUNDED PROJECT

Session title: SatisFactory - A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments

Type of networking spaces: Room (choose the capacity below, 45 minutes time slot). Size: 40 people

Objective of the proposed session

The SatisFactory networking session aims to promote novel ICT technologies for industry (such as Augmented Reality and Incident Detection System) and to discuss how to improve both factories efficiency and workers' satisfaction.

A 4.0 industrial revolution is underway with the introduction of new digital technologies within smart factories. The SatisFactory project plans to incorporate a set of cutting-edge technologies in industrial assembly lines to provide labourers with real-time informational support for incident management, maintenance and training. Data will be collected by a sensor network, processed by a centralized analysis system and ultimately redistributed to the concerned operatives via Augmented Reality glasses and other connected interfaces.

The networking session will constitute an open forum to present the project solutions, to share ideas and to discuss challenges around the topic of "ICT for industry".

Description of the format

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The participation of visitors will be sought thanks to open discussions on societal and technological aspects: How do you see the future of factory workers in terms of activities and working conditions? This question falls within the framework of two broader issues that the SatisFactory project will strive to make mutually compatible: How to improve happiness at work? And how to enhance the productivity and flexibility of factories in Europe? These debates will be illustrated by a presentation of solutions developed in the SatisFactory project. The project is developing emerging technologies for training and incident management (e.g. augmented reality, customized communication platforms, gamification techniques, etc.). During the discussion, visitors may be selected for real-time testing of Augmented Reality Glasses designed for industry and for providing feedback on their impressions.

Who would attend your networking session?

SatisFactory's networking session aims to attract any visitor interested in 1) innovative approaches and technologies for modernizing the European industry and in 2) promoting working environments focused on team building and workers satisfaction.

The following people are specifically targeted: The scientific community involved in manufacturing, ICT, or Augmented Reality technologies (in particular the Factories of the Future community); Industry stakeholders from various sub-sectors such as automotive, energy, etc.; Policy-makers working on the industry sector; and, more generally, any stakeholder interested in ICT for industry and workers' well-being.

How will you attract participants?

The attention of participants will be gained thanks to a visual immersion in industrial workplaces, through photos, videos and explanations regarding SatisFactory two pilot plants. The context in which the SatisFactory solutions are developed will be highlighted through a presentation of current challenges of the industry sector, such as the need to improve the competitiveness and attractiveness of European industries. The SatisFactory solutions will be presented through live demonstrations and visitors will discover more of these technologies aiming to improve real-time informational support and training of workers. The session will end with an open discussion on how visitors see the future of workers; how to improve happiness at work; and how to enhance the productivity and flexibility of factories in Europe.

Expected outcome

The expected outcomes of the session include a large number of stakeholders being more aware of ideas and technologies for building the industrial future of Europe; scientists, researchers and manufacturers convinced that they should pay a special attention in enhancing the quality and attractiveness of working environment in factories, and in making them attractive to young talents; if possible, economic and policy decision-makers encouraged in supporting the industrial economy and employment in Europe by promoting novel ICT technologies for industry; lastly, and above all, new, disruptive ideas, concepts and solutions for the enhancement of work life, especially in factories.